

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ALTERNATIVE TECHNOLOGIES OF CANNED MEAT PRODUCTION IN KAZAKHSTANI MARKET

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Abstract

Investigated retort packaging as an alternative to the classic technology of canned meat products in traditional tin and glass jars.

Keywords: retort packaging, canned food, meat products, quality, storage.

INTRODUCTION

The Kazakhstan production concept for canned meat still uses the traditional method of packaging, which includes the use of thin sheet tin cans coated with tin protected with an anti-corrosion varnish. Recently, this method has been replaced by double aluminum tin packaging, where the steel base is coated on both sides with an aluminum anti-corrosion layer. In some production variations, especially for canned meat and premium products, glass containers may also be used. However, these types of packaging, as part of modern canned meat production, subject to increasing consumer demand and the introduction of marketing strategies, have quite specific characteristics.

Retort packaging is packaging made of polymeric and combined materials designed for packaging canned products. In recent years, both in our country and abroad, there has been an increasing interest in such packaging [1].

The primary function of packaging is protection from the environment: from dust, sunlight, air oxygen, moisture, microbial contamination, etc. To perform this function, the packaging must be leak-proof, corrosion-resistant, chemically inert, durable, etc. An important factor is economy, which implies not only saving materials for the package itself, but also a minimum of

technological costs in the manufacture of products, saving storage space during storage, fuel during transportation [2].

During production, the use of retort packaging can reduce the duration of sterilization, because the contact area with the internal contents is three times higher compared to other containers and is 40-90 minutes. The thermal stability of polymers allows to exclude the release of chemical elements in the product under prolonged exposure to high temperatures, which results in: reduced energy consumption, improved organoleptic indexes, low risk of food poisoning. Duration of storage in such packaging varies from half a year to three years [3].

Today, packaging for meat and meat products must not only guarantee the freshness and safety of the product, the preservation of nutrients, to be convenient for transportation, but also to have an attractive design [4].

EXPOSITION

We prepared new canned meat products (Table 1) using trimmed beef with a mass fraction of adipose and connective tissue of not more than 14%, obtained when cutting beef of the first and second categories in half carcasses and quarters (GOST 34120), in cuts (GOST 31797); black pepper (GOST 29050); dry bay leaf (GOST 17594); iodine salt (GOST 13830).

Table 1.

The formulation of new canned meat

Ingredients	Xi	Formulation, kg	Mass fraction, %				Price, tg/kg	The content of the components in the recipe, kg				Price, tg	Energetic value, kkal
			fat	protein	carbohydrate	water		fat	protein	carbohydrate	water		
I grade beef	X1	87,0	16,00	18,60	0,00	65,00	2800,0	13,92	16,18	0,00	56,55	243600,00	190,01
Raw fat	X2	10,0	100,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	500,0	10,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	5000,00	90,00
Bay leaf	X3	1,00	12,54	8,4	48,7	5	700,0	0,13	0,08	0,487	0,05	700,00	3,28885
Black Pepper peas	X4	1,00	3,3	10,4	38,7	12	3850,0	0,03	0,10	0,387	0,120	3850,00	2,1643
Salt	X5	1,00	0	0,0	0	0,2	155,0	0,00	0,00	0	0,002	155,00	0
Total		100,00											
Composition of the product, %			24,1	16,4	0,9	56,7		24,1	16,4	0,9	56,7	253305,00	
Goal function							253305,00					Energetic value, kkal	285,46

The technology of new canned meat production consists of the following processes (Fig. 1):

Fig. 1. Technological scheme of new canned meat

The technological process of production new canned meat was carried out in the Experimental-educational laboratory of «Canning Technology» (Fig. 2) of Almaty Technological University.

Fig. 2. The Technological process of production of new canned meat

Fig.3. JSC Almaty Technological University. Research Laboratory for Assessing the Quality and Safety of Food Products.

Name of indicators,units of measurement	Actual results
Physico-chemical indicators:	
-mass fraction of protein,%	17,44
-mass fraction of fat,%	2,84
-mass fraction of carbohydrates,%	-
Energy value, kkal	95,32
Mineral elements:	
-aluminum,mg/kg	-

After storing our manufactured product for 6 months, we submitted it for analysis to determine the physico-chemical and energy value of the product. (Fig.3)

We studied physico-chemical and organoleptic indicators (Fig. 4) of new canned meat products. The analyzed samples of canned meat generally exhibited the expected taste and aroma of seasoned beef without any undesirable smells or aftertastes. When heated, the canned meat appeared as irregularly shaped meat pieces, primarily weighing over 30 g, devoid of tough connective tissue, large blood vessels, and lymph nodes, immersed in broth. The meat slices maintained their form or partially broke apart upon removal from the jar. The meat had a moist and tender texture. As for

the heated broth, it exhibited a light brown color and contained suspended protein particles in the form of flakes, resulting in a cloudy appearance.

The amount of protein and fat were 16.5 g and 15.4 g respectively in 100 g new canned meat products. The organoleptic assessment was carried out in the "Technology of food products" department according to the relevant standards according to 5 indicators: smell, taste, color, consistency and general evaluation. New canned meat corresponded to all organoleptic indicators according to the state standard. In conclusion, according to the new developed recipe, we can expand the range of canned meat in retort packaging in our country.

Fig. 4. The organoleptic evaluation of new canned meat

CONCLUSION

Therefore, a viable approach for enhancing the production of canned meat would involve shifting towards polymer-based packaging and gradually phasing out traditional and glass packaging. In connection with these features, we had the task to develop and justify the technology of canned meat in retort packaging at different modes of sterilization of products, with its subsequent storage. It is also a task to study changes in the main microbiological, physico-chemical and organoleptic indicators of canned meat in the retort package during long-term storage. For the purpose of development of food products of the country of Kazakhstan, it is considered a great product, convenient for transportation, and materially efficient.

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